

DAMAGE PHENOMENA OF FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES UNDER VHCF-LOADING

M. Gude¹, W. Hufenbach¹, I. Koch^{1*}, R. Koschichow¹
K. Schulte², J. Knoll²

¹Institute of Lightweight Engineering and Polymer Technology, TU Dresden, Germany

²TU Hamburg-Harburg, Institute M-11 Polymer Composites, Denickestrasse 15, 21073 Hamburg, Germany

* Corresponding author (ilja.koch@tu-dresden.de)

Keywords: VHCF, carbon fibre, damage phenomena

1 Introduction

Due to their high specific static and fatigue strength, carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) are predestined for applications in lightweight structures under cyclic loading. In the case of the main spar of state-of-the-art wind turbine blades unidirectional carbon fibre reinforcement is in use. To achieve a maximum efficiency by extended in-service times, more than 10^9 load cycles have to be resisted without damage [1]. Common fatigue experiments for acquiring verified material data at test frequencies up to 20 Hz do not lead to satisfying results within a reasonable test time. But higher test frequencies well above 20 Hz lead to significant warming and undesired premature failure of the specimen.

Within the priority program SPP1466 the development of adapted test principles for the characterisation of the VHCF phenomena and, in a second step, the development of damage models for advanced materials such as non crimped carbon fibre reinforced composites (T300/LY556) as a basis for novel fatigue life evaluation methods is aimed at.

2 VHCF-test stand

The main obstacle in high frequency testing of CFRPs is the thermal heating due to the comparably high material damping. Whereas at tension/compression loading in fibre direction the dissipated energy is relatively low, the amount of shear deformation in the polymer matrix material due to in-plane and out-of-plane shear loading is responsible for significant internal heating. Furthermore, the loaded material

volume has to be minimised for achieving a low equilibrium temperature of the vibrating specimen and the surrounding climate.

Using a shear force free bending setup according to Fig. 1, both demands can be satisfied. A slender and layered bending specimen is restrained by ball joints and loaded with an eccentric mass and a spring. The setup is excited perpendicularly to the specimen by a forced oscillation with a shaker system. To avoid the development of axial stresses the bearing play is specifically adjusted.

Fig. 1: VHCF-bending test stand

For the real time control, the test stand is equipped with eddy current sensors measuring the position of both eccentric masses at a sampling rate of 150 kHz. By monitoring the vibration amplitude, mean and phase shift of both masses the most important operating parameters of the test stand are displayed. A feedback to the shaker control system is applied to stop the vi-

bration test in case of overloads or critical phase shifts between the left and the right eccentric mass.

3 Specimen design and first results

With the help of the finite element method the specimen is designed to achieve a homogeneous stress distribution and to force damage in selected failure modes only.

Therefore the idealised FE model of the test stand is loaded by a rotation restraint of 0.125 rad. By studying the failure mode specific material effort according to the Failure Mode Concept (FMC) of *CUNTZE* [2] for static loading, here, exemplary the performance of waisted specimens with a tangential or circular notch is analysed. The calculation results are furthermore compared to the experimentally observed failure behaviour of selected specimens.

Using the circular notch geometry (according to Fig. 2), a more homogeneous stress distribution and generally lower material effort are achieved. The desired fibre failure modes in tension and compression (FF1 and FF2) show the highest values compared to other failure modes. At the same time the undesired shear stresses in the area of the notch radius are significantly reduced.

Fig. 2: Comparison of the failure mode specific material effort and the resulting damage phenomenology ((a) – tangential (PK 13) and (b) – circular notch (PK 34))

The damage phenomenology of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced specimens fit very well to the numerically obtained results.

In Fig. 3 the load cycle dependent graphs of the mean displacement a of the eccentric masses (measured by eddy current sensors) are displayed. The first inter fibre failure, which has been measured as well as visibly monitored on the specimen, is marked by A and A' respectively. In case of the tangential waisting this point of damage initiation (A) has been recorded significantly earlier compared to the specimen with the circular waist (A').

Fig. 3: Mean displacement a of the specimens PK 13 (tangential waist) and PK 34 (circular waist)

In analogy to the specimens with axial fibre reinforcement, currently the specimen design is being adapted and the experimental characterisation regarding the failure modes IFF1 and IFF3 in VHCF tests with 90°-reinforced specimens is performed.

4 Optimised VHCF-test stand for large deformations

Using the described experimental setup a maximum strain of about 0.5 % on the specimen surface can be achieved. In case of carbon fibre reinforcements and nano particle modified epoxy systems with high breaking elongation well above 1 % a fatigue failure in evenly stressed areas is not initiated until 10^8 cycles.

Additionally, the main obstacle of a pure torque induced bending test stand, the overstressing in

the area of the force introduction, leads to accelerated damage and failure close to the specimen clamping. The overstressing was significantly reduced by specific specimen designs but not solved to full satisfaction (see section 3).

For the fatigue analysis above 0.5 % strain a modified shear force free VHCF bending test stand with the focus on large deformations and build in axial guiding has been designed and numerically validated.

The new test stand concept is based on the idea of the group for mechanisms theory of the TU Dresden [3] who plotted the pole curve of a shear force free bending experiment which found to be a straight line (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: Pole curve analysis of a shear force free cantilever beam deformation experiment

Furthermore it has been found, that every planetary gear with a gear ratio of $\omega_1/\omega_2 = 1$ shows a similar pole curve. The preferable gear for the given problem has been synthesised keeping the specimen geometry constant with two rotatable gears and clamping positions on a constant radius (l_l). The resulting configuration showing the specimen in undeformed and deformed position is given in Fig.5.

Fig. 5: Principle test stand configuration for a shear force free bending experiment considering large deformations and build in axial guiding [3]

A mechanical representation of this approach was found by abstracting the conventional test stand. The clamping area is now shifted outside of the axis of rotation. In parallel it acts as eccentric mass for the torque load introduction during the acceleration by the shaker system (see Fig. 6). In contrast to the test stand principle shown in Fig. 5 the mechanical coupling between the axis of rotation has been omitted avoiding undesired play and wear during the fatigue experiments.

Fig. 6: Optimised test stand design

This assumption is reasonable due to the symmetry of the specimen and the acceleration based loading equally on both ends of the specimen.

5 Numerical validation of the new design

The basic dimensions of the new test stand design have been synthesised using analytical approaches according to [3]. The numerical simulation of the resulting test stand with constant restraint of 0.25 rad rotation at both axes have shown, that again overstressing of the specimen in the area of the clamping due to very localised force introduction occurs (see Fig. 7).

To reduce the local stress peaks the distance between the axis of rotation and the clamping (l_i) have been modified to smaller as well as larger distances. It could be shown, that a slightly larger distance compared to the analytical solution reduces the stress concentrations significantly. The reason for this effect is the extended axial dilatation compared to the theoretically calculated value which results in reduced torque introduction into the specimen. The additional arising axial forces lead to a shift of the specimen deformation from the ideal cylindrical to a more parabolic form. According to Fig. 7 the clamping areas are now significantly relieved. The positions of the highest strain in fibre direction (ϵ_{11}) as well as of the mean strain (ϵ_{mean}) are shifted, as required, towards the middle of the rectangular specimen. The shear stress level in the specimen is still very low. Hence significant energy dissipation from this source is not expected during the test. Therefore the new test stand design offers the opportunity to use rectangular specimens which are easy to produce. Moreover the influence of stress concentrations and undesired failure modes due to notches and waists are avoided.

Fig. 7: Strain field in fibre direction (top) as well as the mean strain (bottom) for cylindrical deformation (restraint 0.25 rad)

Fig. 8: Strain field in fibre direction (top) as well as the mean strain (bottom) for parabolic deformation (restraint: 0.25 rad)

6 Examples for the damage phenomenology in fatigue loading

For the validation of the VHCF bending test setup developed, standard tension-tension fatigue experiments in fibre direction on servo-hydraulic testing machines and moderate loading frequency have been performed. The damage mechanism in case of fatigue loading in fibre direction is displayed in Fig. 9. Subfigure 9a displays a rough failure surface in different levels, which is typical for brittle fibre reinforced composites [4]. The failure surface of a single filament is displayed exemplary in subfigure 9b. The crack propagation direction is clearly visible, starting from the filament edge and propagating radially through the filament diameter. In

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case of the failure of multiple filaments (Fig. 9c) the failure initiation point may be found in the area of a direct contact between two filaments. The crack propagates in different direction bridging to other filaments directly or in form of debonding and matrix failure.

Exemplary for the damage phenomenology during fatigue bending loading perpendicular to the fibre direction, SEM-pictures near the specimen surface are displayed in Fig. 10. The fatigue bending experiments have been performed on the VHCF-test stand described in section 2. Due to the comparably low stiffness of these specimens the test frequency reached $f = 50$ Hz. The specimen survived $5 \cdot 10^5$ load cycles until crack initiation beginning from the

surface.

On top of the specimen a resin layer of about $150 \mu\text{m}$ in thickness can be seen. Within the polymer matrix lines of rest may be recognised (Fig. 10c). Within the fibre reinforced material the crack is mainly growing by interface failure. The filaments can clearly be seen and only less relicts of matrix on the fibres are recognisable. For the case of matrix failure, such as between filaments, significant plastic deformations, recognisable by cusps and highly deformed pieces of matrix, are observed. For the VHCF regime with less strain and longer fatigue life, crack growth accompanied with plastic deformation such as shown in Fig. 10 may shift to brittle failure. Unfortunately experimental

Fig. 9: SEM-pictures of a CFRP fatigue failure surface ($f = 6$ Hz, $R = 0,1$): (a) Failure surface perpendicular to the fibre direction and loading, (b) single failed filament, (c) failure propagation in adjacent filaments

Fig. 10: Bending fatigue failure surface of a specimen reinforced in 90° direction only, SEM-pictures with rising resolution from subfigure a) to c) ($f = 50$ Hz, $R = -1$, $N = 5 \cdot 10^5$ cycles)

evidence to this hypothesis is still missing.

7 Conclusion

The development of reliable fatigue life evaluation methods for non-crimped carbon fibre reinforced epoxy at extremely high load cycles requires a deep understanding of the successive damage behaviour and the occurring damage mechanisms. For the failure mode specific fatigue testing shaker based fatigue test stands as well as adapted test specimens are developed. The presented shaker based VHCF test stands are now used for the characterisation of the fatigue behaviour of carbon fibre reinforced composites at high frequency loading in fibre as well as perpendicular to the fibre direction.

The first VHCF-bending fatigue experiments show promising results. It has been shown that the crack growth due to alternating tension stresses perpendicular to the fibre direction is dominated by interface cracking as well as plastic deformation in the polymer matrix. For smaller strain amplitudes and life cycles larger than 10^8 cycles a change of the damage mechanism in the polymer matrix is expected.

5 Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the German Research Foundation (DFG) within the Priority Program SPP 1466.

References

- [1] Nijssen, R. P. L. Fatigue life prediction and strength degradation of wind turbine rotor blade composites. PhD thesis, Delft University, 2007
- [2] Cuntze, R.: The predictive capability of failure mode concept-based strength criteria for multi-directional laminates – Part B. Composites Science and Technology 64 (2004), S. 487-516
- [3] Modler, N.; Modler K.-H.; Hufenbach, W. A.; Jaschinski, J.; Zichner, M.; Hanke, U.; Ehlig, J.: Optimization of a test bench for testing compliant elements under shear-force-free bending load. Procedia Materials Science Volume 2, 2013, pp 130–136
- [4] Greenhalgh, E.S.: *Fracture analysis and Fractography of polymer composites*. CRC Press, Cambridge, 2009.